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FAILURE ANALYSIS OF TIRE MOUNTED CRANE

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ABSTRACT

In construction industry, maintenance costs accounts for 10-15% of the production cost. Maintenance affects the targets, quality and profitability of the plant.

Mobile crane maintenance is one of important factor enhancing the productivity in construction plant. Mobile crane breakdown is responsible for high down time lost. To avoid unwanted down time maintenance programs should be capable to minimize breakdown.

After analysis of existing maintenance procedure & maintenance cost of Hydraulic Mobile crane at different running hours it was found that some critical items of Mobile crane were failed before its life cycle. After failure analysis of some critical items of hydraulic mobile crane it was found that the failure of components takes place only due to lack of knowledge of maintenance procedure to the operator. Because operator play key role to maintain machine safe, reliable at minimum maintenance cost. This can only possible when the operator having full knowledge about safe operation, repair & maintenance procedure.

INTRODUCTION:

PREAMBLE

It is the need of the present day for the equipments to handle heavy loads with fast speed, reliability, safety & economy. Mobile cranes are a heavy load lifting machine. Mobile crane are available from load rating capacity of 10 tones to 200 tones. Its cost varies from 25 lacs to 120 lacs. Due to very high

initial cost, running cost and maintenance cost, it is necessary to maintain its safe, reliable and economic operation at low maintenance cost with least rate of failures.

OBJECTIVE OF PRESENT WORK

The aim of this work is to increase overall equipment effectiveness. Greater safety, longer equipment life and minimum life cycle cost with the help of failure analysis of critical items and its proper preventive maintenance. To ensure failure free operation of mobile cranes, it is necessary to design & develop planned maintenance system on the basis of failure analysis of critical items. This work covers failure analysis of under carriage parts of crane, such as boom bushes, pins, as well as super structure parts such as Boom & cylinder Attachment. On the basis of failure analysis of said parts, some recommendations are given to prevent their futuristic failure. ..preventive maintenance procedure to increases life cycle with least failures at minimum cost.

By identifying significant risk factors, problem areas can be revealed and construction contractors can take suitable action. By using accepted techniques of both safety or risk management and maintenance management, performance in both areas can be improved. Effective maintenance programs have been proven to enhance both safety performance (**Hartmann, 1992**), and decrease maintenance costs (**Fredendall, 1997**). In addition, by using proactive maintenance techniques companies can legitimately expect to achieve value added results form their maintenance department expenditures (**Tajiri, 1992**).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The purpose of this study is to develop a maintenance plan for cranes and heavy equipment that improves safety and efficiency. Most of the Construction industries is experiencing problems with it is cranes and heavy equipment that are creating risks to humans and property. These problems are costing the company money. It is suspected that these problems are related the improper maintenance of their cranes and heavy equipment. Construction industry believes that improving their equipment maintenance procedures will improve these conditions.

However, there was very little information found in the search for a construction equipment maintenance program. A comprehensive search was conducted through articles and books with no results. An electronic database and World Wide Web search yielded similar results. Electronic (e-mail) polling of the major construction contractors, equipment manufacturers and crane certification organizations produced only maintenance manuals for specific machines. There were no comprehensive maintenance plans available for contractors in the construction business.

This necessitates formulating a plan by focusing on successful safety and maintenance plans used in industrial settings. The construction industry is usually slow to adopt new management techniques, with many contractors being entrepreneurial in nature and priding ability to scramble through a myriad of adversities and risks (**Palmer, 1996**). These construction industry leaders realize the need to extract maximum efficiency from their company's assets. In the industrial sector, notably on the overhead cranes used in the paper industry, proactive maintenance techniques have been developed that have dramatically improved safety and efficiency in their overhead cranes.

Along with these improvements, they have been able to reduce expenses, and create value added improvements in their equipment for every maintenance dollar spent (**Sothard, 1996**).

Today's optimal maintenance program must not only remediate risk factors but also demonstrate a measurable return on capital invested (**Sothard, 1996**). By identifying significant risk factors, problem areas can be revealed and construction contractors can take suitable action. By

using accepted techniques of both safety or risk management and maintenance management, performance in both areas can be improved. Effective maintenance programs have been proven to enhance both safety performance (**Hartmann, 1992**), and decrease maintenance costs (**Fredendall, 1997**).

Mobile Cranes

Introduction

There are many types of Cranes available to suit our site work needs. For low rise building, we might only using the mobile crane or truck crane to assist our site hoisting work. There are many types of mobile crane itself. 16 tons, 20 tons, 25 tons, 25ton, 45 tons, 60 tons, 80 tons, 100 tons, 130 tons, 160 tons and 200 tons depend on local suppliers.. To determine which type of crane you need, you are required to know what are you hoisting and the site access cum condition. Experience will guide you to choose the idea crane for your site and to cut the construction cost as well.

Hydraulic Crawler Crane

Other than that, we got hydraulic crawler crane, ship cranes, offshore cranes, Tower crane, Luffing Tower crane.

Increased crane operating radius for lifting tilt-up panels

Components of Mobile crane

Mobile crane (P&H RK-200)

COMPONENT NAME

1. Hydraulic Pump
2. Radiator & Oil Cooler
3. Air Cleaner
4. Outrigger
5. Float
6. Boom Telescopic Cylinder
7. Boom hoist cylinder
8. Boom
9. Fuel tank
10. Hydraulic oil tank
11. Engine
12. Counter weight
13. Jib
14. Winch Motor
15. Main winch drum
16. Aux. winch drum
17. Battery
18. Operator's room (CAB)
19. Torque Converter
20. Transmission

CAB FEATURES

- 1 Left control lever/ horn switch (on top of lever)
- 2 Left travel pedal
- 3 Left travel lever
- 4 Right travel lever
- 5 Right travel pedal
- 6 Right control lever/ power boost switch (on top of lever)
- 7 Front right panel
- 8 Right console
- 9 Air conditioners panel - if equipped
- 10 Operator's seat
- 11 Cab door release lever
- 12 Left console
- 13 Pilot control sheet off lever
- 14 Fuse box
- 15 Hour meter

Components of Mobile Crane

Instrument Installation- Hydraulic Power

- Bourden tube Pressure Gauges
- Pressure limiting Valves
- Gauge Restrictors
- Steady State Pressure transducers
- Diaphragm based transducers

Instrument Installation - Electrical Power

Dual Coil Wattmeter

Electromechanical Wattmeter
Single Phase Wattmeter
Current & Voltage Transformers
Hall Effect Transistors
Magnetic Field Sensing Elements

Instrument Installation – Torque And Speed

Strain Gauges
Torque Transducers
Electronic Crystal Frequency-Tachometer
Squirrel cage induction motors

Instrument installation-Temperature

Temperature Transducers
Thermocouples
Platinum Resistance Temperature Sensors
Thermistors
Small integrated circuit temperature sensors

Vibration Monitoring

Vibration monitoring is generally the key component monitoring of the most condition monitoring programs. However vibration-monitoring monitoring cannot provide all the information the mechanical condition of the equipment and not other critical parameters required to maintain the reliability and efficiency of machinery. It is therefore a very limited tool for monitoring the critical process and machinery efficiencies and other parameters that can severely limit productivity and product quality. Thus a comprehensive programme must include other monitoring diagnostic technique aside from vibration monitoring. These including thermography, tribology, process parameter monitoring, visual inspection and many other non-destructive testing techniques.

Vibration analysis is the dominant technique used for condition monitoring programme. Consequently since the greatest population of the typical equipment is mechanical, this technique of the widest application and benefits of the total plant programme,

Common Problems causes vibrations are:

- (a) Imbalance of rotating parts
- (b) Eccentric components
- (c) Misalignments of couplings and bearings
- (d) Bent shafts
- (e) Components looseness
- (f) Worn or damaged gears
- (g) Bad drive belts and drive chains
- (h) Bad antifriction bearings
- (i) Torque variations
- (j) Electromagnetic forces

(k) Aerodynamic forces

(l) Hydraulic forces

Failure of Hydraulic Hoses, Its Causes and Remedies

HYDRAULIC HOSES

HYDRAULIC HOSES

Observation	Causes	Remedy
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Damage • Deformation • Oil leak • Looseness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressure 300 bar • Stress Permanent • Due to wear & tear • Season variation & temperature variation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hose should replace every 24 months. • Protect • Clean

Failure of Bush, Its Causes and Remedies

BUSH

BUSH

Failure of Swing Bearing, Its Causes and Remedies

Swing Bearing

After failure analysis of above Hydraulic mobile crane parts it is found that the above problems were arise due to lack of knowledge of the operator related to correct inspection, operation and maintenance programs at the time when the machine was hand overed to operator

Hence, it is necessary to train the operator before machine is to be handover to him.

In present work, I have given some recommendations to M/s Punjlloyd Ltd., Banmore related to correct inspection, safe operation and maintenance procedures so that the failure of future events can be minimized.

CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE SCOPE

As we know, nowadays competition is very high and also increasing day by day. Thus to survive in the market the machinery must be maintained safe, reliable & economic operation at minimum maintenance cost with least rate of failures.

Safe, reliable & economic operation of earthmoving equipment cannot be ensured without regular safety inspections and thorough preventive maintenance programs. A thorough inspection program can forecast maintenance needs or potential equipment failure or malfunctions. The lack of such a program could result in serious deterioration of the equipment, or repair charges as well as on increased potential for accidents.

In present work an effort has been done to reduce failure rates of critical items of Hydraulic Mobile crane. Because of failure of components does not only increase the maintenance cost but also increases breakdown time & decreases production.

In Punjlloyd Ltd., Ban more, I have collected some data related to failed components of undercarriage parts such as bush, pins, as well as superstructure parts such as boom & cylinder of crane. I have found that these components were failed at 1886 running hour. But as per recommendation by manufacturer of Hydraulic mobile crane these parts should not failed before 6500 running hours.

The failure of above critical items of hydraulic mobile crane does not only increase maintenance cost but also losses production in large quantity, because machine breakdown time was 7 days when they failed.

After failure analysis of above critical items of Hydraulic Mobile crane it was found that the machine components was failed only due to lack of knowledge of maintenance plan to the operator. The operator was not so trained to maintain Hydraulic Mobile crane in safe condition.

In the present work a case study is discussed in which a problem of hydraulic mobile crane and its modification is covered.

Hydraulic Mobile crane is a heavy load lifting machine. Crane breakdown is responsible for high down time lost. To avoid unwanted downtime maintenance programs should be capable to minimize breakdown.

For future work it is necessary to analysis failures of superstructure & attachment components of hydraulic Crane so that the mean time between failures can be increased with least maintenance cost & increases production.

For future scope, it is also essential that machinery problems be detected early enough to plan repair actions and to minimize machine breakdown time. The techniques involves for prediction of failures,

called predictive maintenance. If it is possible to predict failure of components, the need of the breakdown and the emergency maintenance can be reduced to greater extent.

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